

Charge Transfer Complexes of Iodine with Oxygenated Donors—Ethers and Ketones. Transition State Structure and Dipole Moment of the Charge Transfer State

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Charge transfer complexes of a few ethers and ketonic compounds with iodine were studied. Charge transfer reactions were manifested in anisole (ether), acetophenone and acetone (ketones). The reaction was studied both spectrophotometrically and conductometrically.

In a previous communication¹ we had shown that the charge transfer reactions observed in the case of aza-aromatics and iodine system can be utilized successfully to demonstrate the behaviour of "outer complex" and "inner complex" by varying the dielectric constant of the solvents. Ethers and ketones having oxygen lone-pair electrons are expected to behave in the same fashion. Since Mulliken² in his classic paper guessed the existence of a chemical reaction in these systems various authors³⁻⁶ often suggested the existence of 1:1 molecular complex of ethers and ketones with iodine but no systematic investigation on the charge transfer reactions in these systems has been carried out. Our object in the present investigation is to see whether we can follow up the charge transfer reactions and isolate the "outer" and "inner" complexes in these systems as in the aza-aromatics + I₂ systems.

In line with the observations of the aza-aromatics and iodine, the following type of reaction mechanism for the oxygenated solvents with iodine may be proposed.

Ethers + I₂ reaction :

Ketones + I₂ reaction :

The formation of outer complex as shown in reactions (1) and (5) can be established by the appearance of a new blue shifted iodine band in nonpolar solvents like cyclohexane. The reactions

(2) and (6) can be studied by changing the polarity of the solvent, thus enhancing the ionization power of the system.

As the "outer complex" goes over to the "inner complex" the charge separation is more and hence the dipole moment of the "inner complex" should be higher than that of the "outer complex". The "inner complex" is assumed here as the intermediate state in the overall reaction scheme and this being a kinetic species, we may apply Eyring's method⁷ to estimate the dipole moment of this transition state. According to Eyring, the reaction rate of a bimolecular reaction of the type

can be related to the dielectric constant of the solvents used and the dipole moments of the reaction species, and the activated complex in the following way

$$\log k_1 = \log \left(K \frac{kT}{h} K_0^* \right) - \frac{1}{kT} \frac{D-1}{2D+1} \left[\frac{\mu_A^2}{a_A^3} + \frac{\mu_B^2}{a_B^3} - \frac{\mu_{M^*}^2}{a_{M^*}^3} \right]$$

where k_1 is the specific rate constant, D the dielectric constant of the final solution formed, a_A , a_B , a_{M^*} correspond to the Onsager cavity radius, K' the transmission coefficient, k the Boltzmann constant and K_0^* the equilibrium constant expressed in terms of the partition functions, the nonelectrostatic terms being considered to be small.

It appears therefore that the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ should be linear if the proposed mechanism is correct. The dipole moment of the transition state may also be estimated from the linear plot if the dipole moment of A and B are known. This relation has been verified by a number of workers⁸⁻¹¹. With this object in view we have measured the specific rate constant for a number of ether-iodine and ketone-iodine reactions in solvents of different dielectric constants both by conductivity

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measurements and by optical density measurements and the results are reported here.

Experimental

The ethers used were diphenyl oxide, tetrahydrofuran and anisole. The ketones used were acetone, acetophenone and benzophenone. Diphenyl oxide and acetone were of E. Merck, G. R. grade. Acetophenone and anisole used were of B. D. H. quality. Benzophenone was obtained from A. Tata Roure Dupont Enterprise, and tetrahydrofuran was from Ranbaxy Laboratories Limited, India.

Solvents used were cyclohexane, chloroform, dichloromethane, 1,2-dichloroethane, and N,N-dimethylformamide, all of E. Merck, G. R. grade.

All the liquids were purified by thoroughly drying and then distilling in a system protected from the atmosphere. For tetrahydrofuran and diphenyl ether, caustic potash stick was used for drying. Benzophenone being a solid was purified by several recrystallization. Iodine was purified by sublimation.

Conductivity measurements were made on Philips conductivity bridge with a cell having bright platinum as electrodes. The gap between the

electrodes was 0.1 cm. Spectrophotometric measurements were taken on Beckmann spectrophotometer Model DU using 1 cm silica cell. All measurements were made at $23 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The positions of the blue shifted iodine band for different ethers and ketones in different solvents are shown in Table 1.

For diphenyl oxide and tetrahydrofuran (ethers) and benzophenone (ketone) iodine system, neither the O. D. at the blue shifted iodine band was dependent on time nor the system showed any conductance. So, no kinetic measurements were possible in these systems.

The specific rate constants for the reactions of anisole, acetone and acetophenone with I_2 in different solvents as measured conductometrically as well as spectrophotometrically [at 370 nm (I_2^- band) and at the respective blue shifted iodine band] are shown in Table 2. The reactions are pseudo unimolecular. In all kinetic measurements the concentration of oxygenated compounds was $\sim 5 \times 10^{-3} M$ and that of iodine was $\sim 1 \times 10^{-5} M$.

It may be observed from Table 2 that for anisole-iodine system charge transfer complexation was

TABLE 1—POSITIONS OF THE BLUE SHIFTED IODINE BAND AND MOLAR EXTINCTION CO-EFFICIENTS (ϵ_c) FOR DIFFERENT OXYGENATED DONORS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Donor	Solvent	Band position nm	ϵ_c $l \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Anisole	Cyclohexane	342	10000.00
	Chloroform	397	2500.00
	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	340	1700.00
	1 : 2 Chloroform + dichloromethane	384	1015.00
	Dichloromethane	398	863.90
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	341	214.00
	1,2-Dichloroethane	395	404.00
	N,N-Dimethylformamide	370 (from the beginning)	—
	Cyclohexane	468	1428.57
	Chloroform	444	81.00
Acetophenone	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	454	84.20
	Dichloromethane	429	86.14
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	431	96.50
	1,2-Dichloroethane	420	102.10
	Cyclohexane	454	1428.57
Acetone	Chloroform	440	117.20
	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	450	134.30
	Dichloromethane	448	153.10
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	436	127.80
	1,2-Dichloroethane	440	138.60
Diphenyl oxide	Cyclohexane	397	1818.18
	Chloroform	326	2222.22
	Dichloromethane	322	2564.10
	1,2-Dichloroethane	319	3333.33
	Cyclohexane	472	507.60
Tetrahydrofuran	Chloroform	469	1292.05
	Dichloromethane	464	312.50
	1,2-Dichloroethane	460	4545.45
	Cyclohexane	470	606.06
Benzophenone	Chloroform	456	400.00
	Dichloromethane	452	500.00
	1,2-Dichloroethane	442	555.55

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS IN OXYGENATED DONORS—IODINE COMPLEXES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Donor	Solvent	Sp. rate const. from conductance $k \times 10 \text{ hr}^{-1}$	Sp. rate const. from O.D. data at 370 nm $k \times 10 \text{ hr}^{-1}$	Sp. rate const. at blue shifted iodine band $k \times 10 \text{ hr}^{-1}$
Anisole	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	0.952	0.921	0.892
	1 : 2 Chloroform + dichloromethane	0.979	1.036	1.065
	Dichloromethane	1.570	1.480	1.390
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	1.727	1.612	1.555
	1,2-Dichloroethane	2.015	1.962	1.688
	N,N-Dimethylformamide	11.12	—	—
Acetophenone	Chloroform	4.205	—	—
	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	6.564	—	—
	Dichloromethane	8.060	—	—
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	10.709	—	—
	1,2-Dichloroethane	15.200	—	—
Acetone	Chloroform	5.527	9.948	9.210
	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	9.527	13.818	13.265
	Dichloromethane	10.590	16.790	16.230
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	11.054	17.968	18.186
	1,2-Dichloroethane	11.890	19.280	18.200

followed by charge transfer reaction when the solvent is changed from chloroform ($D=4.72$) to dichloromethane ($D=9.08$). In chloroform, the O.D. of the blue shifted iodine band did not change with time. In dichloromethane, the initial band position at 338 nm was not steady and the O.D. changed with time. This band completely vanished after ~ 2 days and a band at 360 nm appeared. Conductivity also increased with time. The same type of behaviour was observed also with 1,2-dichloroethane ($D=10.65$). With dimethylformamide ($D=35.00$) the anisole+iodine system showed a band at 370 nm from the very beginning. This made it impossible to follow the kinetic rate. The system was studied in two mixed solvents. The compositions of the mixed solvents were (1) chloroform-dichloromethane mixture (1 : 1, v/v) ($D=6.9$) and (2) dichloromethane-dichloroethane mixture (1 : 1, v/v) ($D=9.87$). Only conductance data are shown for dimethylformamide.

The acetone+ I_2 system showed a new band at 440 nm in chloroform. O.D. of this band changed with time and after a few hr a new band at 370 nm appeared. The solution also showed a change of colour from pinkish to yellowish. Conductivity measurements showed an increase in conductance with time. Rate constant data by spectrophotometric (at 440 nm and 370 nm) method, as well as by conductometric method are presented in Table 2. Similar type of behaviour was observed with other solvents, the reactions becoming faster with increasing D of the solvent. The kinetic data for the system were followed in (1) chloroform ($D=4.72$), (2) chloroform-dichloromethane mixture (1 : 1, v/v) ($D=6.9$), (3) dichloromethane ($D=9.08$), (4)

dichloromethane-dichloroethane mixture (1 : 1, v/v) ($D=9.87$) and (5) dichloroethane ($D=10.65$).

For acetophenone+iodine, the charge transfer reactions as manifested from the rate of reactions are much higher than those of the anisole+iodine system. The reaction rate could be followed upto dichloroethane ($D=10.65$); with dimethyl formamide the reaction rate was too fast. Kinetic measurements were made in (1) chloroform, (2) chloroform-dichloromethane mixture (1 : 1, v/v) ($D=6.9$), (3) dichloromethane ($D=9.08$), (4) dichloromethane-dichloroethane mixture (1 : 1, v/v) ($D=9.87$) and (5) dichloroethane ($D=10.68$).

The dipole moment was calculated from the plot of $\log k_1$ against $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ from conductance data for the donors anisole, acetone and acetophenone and the data are recorded in Table 3. The $\log k_1$ and $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ values for the system acetone+iodine, calculated from the O.D. data at 370 nm are also tabulated in Table 3. For acetophenone+ I_2 system, determination of specific rate constants from spectrophotometric measurements were not possible because of high absorption of the donor (absorption of acetophenone is located at 315-318 nm) itself at the absorption maximum of the complex. The position of the band was located by balancing the solution of the complex against the same concentration of the donor. Specific rate constants were determined from the conductance data only.

The plot $\log k_1$ vs $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ for the systems anisole,

TABLE 3— $\log k_1$ vs $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ OF RESPECTIVE SOLVENTS FROM CONDUCTANCE DATA AND SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DATA (CALCULATION OF DIPOLE MOMENT OF TRANSITION COMPLEX)

Donor	Solvent	Dielectric constant (D)	$\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$	$\log k_1$			Dipole moment in the transition state (μ_M^*) in Debye		
				conduc-tance data	O.D. data at 379 nm	O.D. data at blue shifted iodine band	conduc-tance data	O.D. data at 370 nm	O.D. data at blue shifted iodine band
Anisole	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	6.9	0.3986	-1.021	-1.035	-1.0494			
	1 : 2 Chloroform + dichloromethane	7.63	0.4078	-1.009	-0.9844	-0.9725			
	Dichloromethane	9.08	0.4217	-0.804	-0.8297	-0.8570	11.08	10.11	9.72
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	9.87	0.4276	-0.763	-0.7926	-0.8084			
	1,2-Dichloroethane	10.65	0.4329	-0.696	-0.7073	-0.7726			
	N,N-Dimethylformamide	35.00	0.4789	0.046	—	—			
Acetophenone	Chloroform	4.72	0.3563	-0.376					
	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	6.9	0.3986	-0.188					
	Dichloromethane	9.08	0.4217	-0.094			10.18		
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	9.87	0.4276	0.080					
	1,2-Dichloroethane	10.65	0.4329	0.182					
Acetone	Chloroform	4.72	0.3563	-0.258	-0.0023	-0.0357			
	1 : 1 Chloroform + dichloromethane	6.9	0.3986	-0.047	0.1404	0.1227			
	Dichloromethane	9.08	0.4217	0.025	0.2250	0.2103	9.35	9.23	9.12
	1 : 1 Dichloromethane + 1,2-dichloroethane	9.87	0.4276	0.044	0.2544	0.2585			
	1,2-Dichloroethane	10.65	0.4329	0.075	0.2850	0.2601			

acetone and acetophenone are shown in Figs. 1-7. All the curves are drawn by least square fit.

It may be observed that the plots are linear with a positive slope. The dipole moment of the activated complex was estimated from the slope in the same way as was discussed earlier¹.

Fig. 1. Anisole iodine complex from conductance data.

Fig. 2. Anisole iodine complex from O.D. data at 370 nm.

The dipole moment of the donors (acetone, acetophenone and anisole) and the calculated dipole moments of the respective transition complexes are given in Table 4.

As may be observed in Table 3 the dipole moment calculated from conductance measurement

Fig. 3. Anisole iodine complex from O.D. data at blue shifted iodine band.

Fig. 4. Acetophenone iodine complex from conductance data.

Fig. 5. Acetone iodine complex from conductance data.

Fig. 6. Acetone iodine complex from O.D. data at 370 nm.

Fig. 7. Acetone iodine complex from O.D. data at blue shifted iodine band.

TABLE 4—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF THE OXYGENATED DONORS AND THE CORRESPONDING TRANSITION STATE

Donor	Acceptor	Dipole moment of the donor Debye unit	Dipole moment of the transition state Debye unit	b
Anisole	I ₂	1.98	10.80	0.7628
Acetophenone	I ₂	3.02	10.13	0.6805
Acetone	I ₂	2.88	9.28	0.6481

agree fairly well with that calculated from spectrophotometric measurement for the acetone+I₂ and anisole+I₂ systems.

It has been mentioned that the same rate constants and dipole moments are obtained from the spectrophotometric measurement at blue shifted iodine band and at 370 nm. The rate measured from the O.D. values at 370 nm should represent the reaction I⁻+I₂→I₃⁻ and since this is an ionic reaction log k₁ vs 1/D should give a linear plot as reported by Das Gupta and Basu¹¹. In the present case log k₁ vs $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ was linear indicating a non-ionic reaction. This may be due to the fact that I⁻+I₂→I₃⁻ is a very fast reaction and the rate determining step is the rate of formation of I⁻ ion i.e., the rate measured by conductivity measurement.

Quantum mechanically, the interaction of an electron-donor and electron-acceptor may be formulated by saying that when any two such entities get together their joint or combined wave function may be expressed in the form

$$\psi_{(D,A)} = a \psi_{(DA)} + b \psi_{(D+A^-)}$$

where the first term gives the contribution of the no bond structure and the second term gives the contribution of dative charge transfer bond.

It has been found and often discussed that the intervention of an additional substance or agency in these systems can produce a strong complex or a chemical reaction (charge transfer reaction). These are called assisted charge transfer complexes and assisted charge transfer reactions.

For both assisted and unassisted charge transfer reactions, further insight can be obtained by plotting curves of energy against a reaction coordinate, say R. By this is meant roughly the distance between

the donor D and acceptor A, but with the understanding that at each value of R both the electronic structures and the skeletons of D and A have adjusted themselves adiabatically (i.e., smoothly and continuously) to give minimum total energy. With the following curves the main types of behaviour may be illustrated schematically.

The forms of the curves in Fig. 8 are based on the following considerations. At large separations, $a=1$ and $b=0$ in the above equation. With decreasing separations, if b remained 0, exchange

Fig. 8. Energy curves U for charge-transfer reactions between a donor D and an acceptor A. R =reaction coordinate.

repulsion associated with ψ_0 would cause U to rise more and more steeply, beginning as soon as D and A overlap appreciably. Actually, as soon as they begin to overlap, b in general begins to increase and resonance between ψ_0 and ψ_1 increases. This and various polarization effects between D and A tend to cut down more and more the rapid rise of U which would occur for pure unpolarized ψ_0 .

The net outcome should be the curves as shown in Fig. 8, the typical case being only with an "outer complex" and an "inner complex" with a maximum in between, as are well demonstrated in the case of all the aza-aromatics+ I_2 in the previous communication. These maxima or barriers may be identified with activated complexes of chemical kinetics. The inner complexes, when not inaccessibly high yet not stable enough to be end products, may be identifiable with "reaction intermediates". It may be speculated that with the ethers and ketones studied here, the "outer complex" to "inner complex" transformation has been observed with cases having special structural features which is discussed below.

As is evident from Table 2, the presence of charge transfer reactions are dominant in the case of ketonic compounds than in the case of ethers. The oxygen atoms in ethers being in a sp^3 hybridized state possess a more or less saturated character whereas the oxygen atoms in ketonic compounds being in a sp^2 hybridized state possess an unsaturated character. So we may expect that the electron transfer process would be easier in the case of ketonic oxygen having a greater π -character.

In this connection we may notice the geometric structure of charge transfer complex of ethers and

ketones with iodine as proposed by Mulliken as shown in Fig. 9.

[After R. S. Mulliken]

Proposed structure of an ether-iodine complex.

[After R. S. Mulliken]

Proposed structure of a ketone-iodine complex.

Fig. 9.

Hassel's crystal structure determination of acetone-bromine complex are also in accord with the above geometric structure.

In ketones the oxygen being in the sp^2 hybridized state (angle 120°), the iodine molecules must come closer to the oxygen atoms for the effective overlapping with lone pair oxygen orbitals than in the case with ethers where the angle is $109^\circ 28'$ (sp^3 hybridization). Consequently the probability of outer complex surmounting the barrier to go over to inner complex is higher with ketones than with ethers.

Among the ethers, when the donor is changed from diphenyl oxide to anisole, one of the phenyl rings in diphenyl oxide is replaced by one methyl group in anisole. Methyl group is long known as a group which has a strong electron releasing capacity and the phenyl ring behaves as an electron withdrawing group. As a consequence the oxygen atom in anisole possesses a higher electron density than the oxygen atom in diphenyl oxide and tetrahydrofuran. This obviously helps in the electron transfer process and in anisole+ I_2 system the charge transfer complexation process is followed by charge transfer reaction. As was shown the existence of charge transfer reactions in anisole+iodine system was actually observed when the solvent was changed from a lower dielectric chloroform ($D=4.72$) to a higher dielectric dichloromethane ($D=9.08$), and even to a mixture of chloroform and dichloromethane.

Ketones also behaved in a similar fashion. When one of the phenyl groups in benzophenone is replaced by a methyl group acetophenone is obtained and here also the charge transfer complexation is followed by charge transfer reactions. When acetone

was used instead of acetophenone as donor, the charge transfer reaction was more prominent.

The present investigation gives us the dipole moment of 7-10 Debye for the transition state in these systems. The dipole moment is given as

$$\int \psi_{(D,A)} r \psi_{(D,A)} d\tau = a^2 \int \psi_{(DA)} r \psi_{(DA)} d\tau + 2ab \int \psi_{(DA)} r \psi_{(D+A^-)} d\tau + b^2 \int \psi_{(D+A^-)} r \psi_{(D+A^-)} d\tau$$

The first term gives the dipole moment of no bond structure which is just the dipole moment of the constituents, the third term gives the dipole moment of the dative structure which is 15.35 Debye for the constituents separated by 3.2 Å. As there is very little overlap between the no bond and dative structure the second term may be set equal to zero. The present investigation gives us the dipole moment for the transition state. Thus it is possible to calculate b^2 and hence 'b' which gives us the percentage of charge transfer in the transition state. The Table 4 gives the value of 'b' for different complexes. Unfortunately the dipole moment of the ground state of these compounds had not been estimated so far and we can only calculate the percentage of charge transfer in the transition state with this type of analysis. It should be pointed out that all the limitations as pointed out in the previous communication are also present here.

These investigations may be placed on a firmer footing by using many more oxygenated compounds.

But the work is rather limited because of the availability, purity and ease of detection of the more complex organic compounds.

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